

CW17 Report—IoT, Open Data, Software Sustainability and a whole host of collaborative goodness!

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Introduction

[Collaborations Workshop 2017 \(CW17\)](#), #CollabW17, took place at the plush [Leeds University Business School](#) from the 27th to 29th March 2017. Over 80 people attended, and the themes of the workshop were the Internet of Things (IoT), Open Data and Software Sustainability. With an eclectic mix of lightning talks, keynotes, Q&A panels, discussions with speed blogging, collaborative idea sessions, mini workshops & demos, a social programme and a Hack Day it was a feature packed and immersive event.

In the following sections, we give an overview of the different parts of the agenda and details some of the outputs.

Lightning talks

[CW17's lightning talks](#) offered a rapid (read two minutes!) presentation covering a topic from someone very closely involved with the work. With 80 attending, it's not always possible or desirable that everyone does a lightning talk. However, we had 30 lightning talks in total.

They are an excellent way to seed potential collaborators and introduce areas of interest to those attending. We had a new impromptu lightning talk session which allowed people who weren't scheduled to present a talk to give a two minute presentation (no slides required!). This certainly added to the unconference nature of the event and will be kept for future CW's.

There were a range of talks from [IoT architecture](#), [Opening up Humanities data](#) and marking up information to make it easier to [integrate using Schema.org](#)—all very much in line with the workshop themes. There was, of course, the mandatory software sustainability topics. There was also a focus on research software engineering with a mention of the [Second Conference of Research Software Engineers](#) and the opening of a [German RSE chapter](#). Software Citation was also highlighted by one of the authors of the much anticipated '[Software Citation Principles](#)'. The [Software assessment framework](#) was one of a number of lightning talks advocating better software practice through tooling and help. Training and Collaborative working were also highlighted. And there was of course those promoting the participants to get involved in their Hack Day ideas.

There was a lot of information and ideas in a short space of time with much relevance to IoT, Open Data and Software Sustainability, a [scan through the slides](#) and [watching the videos](#) will be a great way to get up to speed with what is happening in the space.

Keynotes

This year we were very fortunate to have three excellent keynote talks on the workshop themes of IoT and Open Data.

IoT ... or Ecosystems of environments

The opening keynote on the [Internet of Things \(IoT\)](#) was delivered by [Usman Haque](#) of Umbrellium fame. Usman delivered a visionary talk: it was not an introduction to IoT but a reflection on his experiences, focusing on the approach he thought successful IoT projects should take. He railed against the command and control nature of current IoT offerings and talked about emergent properties of distributed devices and how their connections with other systems and with people and facilitating connections between people is where the real innovations lie. To put it in Usman's terms, it was out of the messy, heterogeneous and social where the really useful applications will come.

From Usman's perspective, IoT is about many different types of things being able to connect in different ways. Ultimately, building anything IoT based is about empowering citizens to make better decisions while controlling who their data is shared with. By citizens, he meant self-organising groups rather than individuals. These IoT systems are meant to help them go beyond what they thought they could do. These are the driving principles on all the projects Usman has presided over. This is in contrast to the old ideas of machine to machine

communication, or IoT generating data that is of use to only person or organisation (whether remote controls or data going to insurance companies monitoring your driving). Whereas Smart Cities infrastructures could be misused to increase surveillance of people, the real value comes from emergent properties rather than top down diktat—i.e. enabling people with the technology and data to help them support their decisions and take a data oriented approach to check facts about things that matter to them.

Usman talked through six projects - each of them with a different focus but all ultimately about the way in which IoT is enabling People in new, different and important ways.

The first project was [Pachube](#), which has a focus on taking measurements and sharing data. It is one of the first generalised IoT infrastructures. It merges a broker and a time series database. It was used after the [Fukushima nuclear disaster](#): while government data was being supplied to the public with low spatial and temporal frequency, anyone with a radiation sensor was able to connect or put data in Pachube. In this example, the fact that the public's devices measured in different units and people did not have prior training were not a problem as people were interested in trends—e.g. whether values were going up or down, the dirtiness of the data did not matter—people were being empowered by contributing to and being able to see everyone else's data at a much faster pace and higher temporal resolution than their government could offer. People even built apps such as [Japan Geigermap](#) and the [Wind from Fukushima](#), which combined data from Pachube with weather data to show where the radiation might move to next. The Fukushima use case also represented a sociological change where in the public psyche people got used to the idea of the government not doing everything for them.

The second project ([Natural Fuse](#)) is an experiment in IoT supporting distributed decision making when resources are limited. This system involves IoT enabled plants which would offset the carbon used by lamps. The experiment consists of six plants, each connected to a lamp. With the caveat that plants lost lives (and were eventually taken out of the system) if the carbon balance was negative, an interesting result was that the communal use of the lamps was much more responsible as the plants would 'die' if lamps were powered on too much. Selfish decisions were moderated by being held accountable to the community. Interestingly, in one version of the experiment, no accountability naturally led to no cooperation (and a rapidly disappearing pool of plants).

The third project called [Linguine](#) (an operating system for public spaces) is an IoT enabled park in Bradford. Visitors were able to discover the park's reactions to their actions, e.g., lights and fountains would move based on their movements, lights would chase them or run away from them based on the configuration of the park at the time of their visit. The idea was that, at some stage, users would be able to reconfigure the park.

The fourth project in this journey is called [Cinder](#), a collaboration between Umbrellium and children about to start school in a new smart building. This project focused on sensing and embodying. The sensors that measure temperature and solar panel energy production were 'embodied' by a digital cat which the children could interact with on a centrally placed augmented reality display and their laptops. They designed the cat and its behaviours, which

was essentially a lesson on resource management— i.e., feeding the cat based on the amount of solar energy collected. The cat functions as a metaphor for the children to understand how the building works and they felt that Cinder was theirs as they were part of its design process.

The fifth project, [VoiceOver](#), uses IoT but it is more about social enablement aided by technology. The project focuses on connecting people together who are not normally connected and seeing what emergent governing structures came about. It is a social cohesion project: a way of giving a voice to people who felt they do not have one, connecting generations, and getting to know each other. For example, it allows the elder generation to tell the others about the coal mining times. It is built upon a peer-to-peer network where each household agrees to host a node and be part of the network. It took many meetings to bring the project to fruition over two years; with governance questions like 'Should political topics be allowed?' The shared ownership public address system became a reason to talk to neighbours, and poetry and bedtime stories and singing were common broadcasts on the network.

The sixth project, [Thingful](#), is a search engine for the Internet of Things and is focused on discovering and interoperability of IoT resources. Its main focus is how to find, access, integrate and unlock data that is available while the owners of the data remain empowered to decide what resolution (e.g. daily/weekly for time series data) their data is shared at. Thingful made it easier to find data from other existing and competing networks e.g., whether this is about earthquakes, buoys in the ocean, radiation or even connected sea creatures!

So by showing us [measuring. sharing. distributing. deciding. opening. reconfiguring. sensing. embodying. connecting. governing. discovering and interoperability](#), Usman took us on a journey of how IoT should be done. For the natural research software communities of the Institute, this was really a heads up about how they should be thinking about IoT enabled research projects, keeping people at the core and not falling into traditional patterns of command and control architectures. IoT, as Usman put it, to deliver on its promise is an ecosystem of environments with relationships between connected things; it is messy and heterogeneous by nature. However, by embracing the nature of IoT, one can understand better how to make use of it and facilitate emergent use than having a rigid view of what it will do. In that sense, ideal IoT systems support agile and emergent use cases.

Usman's talk is available on the [Institute's YouTube channel](#).

Open Data

For the [Open Data](#) keynote, we were equally fortunate with [Tom Forth](#) as the speaker. Tom helped set up the [Leeds ODI node](#) and has done consultancy work for business and government. Tom's journey began while trying to apply computer vision to malaria research during his PhD. As part of this, he published an influential Wikipedia article by making [Flux Balance Analysis](#) an easier-to-understand subject and wrote a tool to make SBML models ([MetNetMaker](#)). Other experiences then drove him into Open Data with applications in the areas of planning and the influential [Leeds Bins app](#).

Tom raised key points such as the fact that many policy areas have little or no data to back them up (e.g., where to build new houses and how to connect bus routes to jobs). With data becoming more available, there was still the need to package new insights in a way that appealed to policy makers rather than drowning them with detail which is then not actioned.

He also mentioned how Leeds Council just 'got rid' of their data (by making it open) and thus useful tools on top of this data have been built for free. Open Data means that people do not have to ask permission to use the data and enables them to work together in efficient ways.

Tom spoke about an interesting convergence of Open Data and IoT that led to river level monitors using the [LoRaWAN](#) standard and [The Things Network](#). This was 10-20x cheaper than existing methods, thus offering local councils new and cost effective ways of keeping people safe and informed.

Tom also highlighted a couple of interesting sources of data: [Wikidata](#) and [Open Street Map](#) (later Tom mentioned someone at CW17 made him aware of a GIS related data set ([LIDAR](#)), which he was keen to start using). The video of Tom's excellent presentation is available on the [Institute's YouTube channel](#).

Fighting Poverty with Data

[Kenji Takeda](#) of Microsoft Research delivered the [CW17 sponsor keynote](#).

He spoke about the [UN 2030 sustainable development goals](#) and how it is really difficult to achieve them unless one does the seemingly simple task of counting and stratifying people in the areas affected by development needs. He covered three areas where Microsoft and collaborators are helping drive change: Poverty, Water Security and Food Supply.

With regards to the counting and stratifying problem, he mentioned the excellent work done by the [WorldPop](#) project to create accurate demographics for countries where such is difficult to come by. He lifted the lid on their techniques showing how different records, such as anonymised mobile phone records, were combined with machine learning algorithms to help create accurate maps that identify poverty stricken areas that need support.

In the context of water security, Kenji highlighted a collaboration with the University of Oxford led [REACH project](#). As part of the project, [IoT devices were added to water pumps](#) in Kenya to monitor their use and correlate the data collected to other factors, e.g., recent rainfall which caused people to use less safe sources of water. They were able to tell how accessible the groundwater supply is based on how much effort is required at the pump (measured by the IoT device).

Regarding food supply, Microsoft ran the [FarmBeats](#) project in California. Working closely with farmers using sensors and video to monitor crops growth and help them to understand how to increase yield. The work done here is helping to gain insights into feeding the world's growing population. The deployment technology was certainly interesting and scaleable.

Rather than the internet, a local network was setup that used [TV White Space frequencies](#) (e.g. previously used by [Teletext](#)); this allowed ranges of up to five kilometres and speeds of upto 10-100 Mbits, thus supporting video monitoring of farm areas).

Kenji then went on to highlight Microsoft work to support research through tools and technology. He mentioned the easy deployment of [Jupyter notebooks](#) using [Microsoft Azure Notebooks](#), the work done to index the research literature and provide recommenders as part of [Microsoft Academic](#) and the generous [Azure for Research Programme](#), which offers free cloud time to researchers, nearly 1200 projects have benefitted to date.

Kenji also spoke about the Cloud enabled IoT kits—the Microsoft Azure IoT Starter Kit—[Adafruit Feather Huzzah ESP8266](#) (Arduino compatible) which they kindly gave to each attendee at CW17 (Kenji ran a mini workshop on this at CW to cover getting started with the device in more depth).

[Kenji's talk is well worth a watch](#) if you would like to hear more.

Social Programme

As well as the workshop dinner at [University House](#), we also ran a social programme at the CW17; this offered a change of scene for those attending and gave them an opportunity to explore local culture and sites.

We had a [campus tour](#) showing highlights of buildings and waymarks at the University of Leeds this was lead by [Martin Callaghan](#), who was also our local host at Leeds helping with the organisation of CW17. The next morning, folk were up bright and early for a canal walk; the guide was Mike Wallis, a colleague of Martin's and also a member of the Leeds [ARC team](#).

After the main CW17 workshop came to a close and before the CW17 Hack Day started, Martin led a trip to the [Treasures of the Brotherton Library](#), where he had arranged viewing of a special non-public collection.

The Collaborations Workshops social programmes are beneficial for attendees as it allows them to explore local highlights which they would otherwise miss. They get to know more about the place from our local contacts; thus getting a deeper insight into the places where CW takes place.

Discussion Sessions

These sessions give attendees a chance to discuss matters of interest. The possible topics are collected during registration and during the workshop to allow both long standing and nascent ideas to surface. If repeat questions from previous CW's appear, we add them and the associated blog(s) to the CW [FAQ](#) page. You can see which [topics were available](#) for discussion at CW17. The groups of four to six people had 45 minutes to discuss their topic

and then 45 minutes to write a blog post about it. This method of creating outputs from the discussion sessions is called [speed blogging](#).

You can [read the speed blogs](#) to see the outputs from the variety of research software related topics that were discussed. Some of the areas discussed this year include creating environments [which encourage diversity](#), how [Research IT is about adapting quickly](#), how to [trust data from the web](#), how to [make your data more open](#), how [better architectures aid sustainability](#), [heuristics for choosing software stacks](#), how [team based research needs flexible career paths](#), how to [grow your developer community with kind feedback](#) and all about [software metrics](#).

Mini-workshops & Demos

Mini-workshop and demo sessions are longer parallel sessions. They allow more depth on a particular topic, tool or technique such as standards and training. You can see the [list of the mini workshops and demos](#) that took place at CW17.

There was something for everyone at the CW17 mini-workshops and demos. These included data and analysis topics such as [standards for data sharing in Neuroimaging](#), [sharing data effectively through repositories](#) and tools to [analyse 3D vector files](#). [Software assessment](#), [software citation](#) and [software related legal matters](#) were also covered. An overview of the large [EPSRC IoT Research Hub](#) was also given. The practical sessions included [getting started with the Azure Huzzah \(IoT\) Kit IoT](#) (which was kindly supplied by Microsoft to each attendee of CW17) and learning how to [create Software Carpentry Style lesson material](#).

See the [mini workshops page](#) for more information and videos.

Discussion Panels

Panel Q&A on IoT, Open Data and implications for research

The panel members were Usman Haque (Umbrellium), Thomas Forth (imactive), Rosie Higman (Research Data Management, University of Cambridge), Andrew Hufton (Nature), Caroline Jay (University of Manchester), Kenji Takeda (Microsoft) and David De Roure (Petras/Oxford e-Research Centre) and the panel chair was Insitute Director, Neil Chue Hong.

These panel members represented academic, industrial, publisher, library and leader perspectives on IoT and Open data and how they are affecting and will affect research. The panel explored how research would change due to advances in IoT and Open Data. The issues of security and privacy and new European directives such as the [GDPR](#), which are much more punitive for breaches, were also highlighted. There was a consensus that we had to be upfront with how one is going to use the data provided by people and their devices and that ultimately there has to be a shared benefit for providers and users.

Teaching and learning were also a hot topic on the panel from [flipped classrooms](#)—where lectures were more about discussions and questions and people learned from online resources—to critiques around thinking and tendencies to digitise victorian processes, this brought us onto [Connected Curriculum](#), which did away with lab based work, to the counterpoint of people needing lab based experience to understand the environment from which data was collected the was nuanced discussion about the trade-offs in this space.

The discussion then moved on to people's fears around IoT and Open Data. The discussion ranged from the need for more informed ethics (including voices from computer science, social science and ethicists) to the need to be less risk averse. [The danger of changing behaviour by people acting on new data was also highlighted](#). Thinking about our work up front, thinking about how new data might be used or misused is necessary to take us from the responsible use of data to [responsible innovation](#). Ethics in the public space is also about the often overlooked tradeoff between data and money, with many people choosing free (over paying any amount of money) and trading their data. However, it was highlighted that University research environments are not subject to this tradeoff, so publicly funded research should make use of such privileges.

There was a big discussion about publishing data which was then exploited by others with the original collectors of the data then left behind. Points around unethical science (sitting on data) were mentioned; others thought there should be a halfway house which gives the original researcher some time (embargo) to get more from their data before it is (auto) published (e.g., after two years). It was felt that as research was not a private enterprise but publically funded whatever solution was put in place for research data availability had to be good for research as well as the researchers. Also, the ever-increasing requirement for researchers to be experts in so many techniques, procedures and legal matters was highlighted leading the feeling that specialist roles (such as [RSE](#)'s) need to be properly supported to make the research process more manageable.

Among other topics, the panel highlighted the need for incentives around data and access; should you get more for contributing? What about correct interpretation? The need for data and good documentation (e.g., describing how it can be used) was also raised. Services such as [Vivli](#) (from Harvard) which are trying to make safe environments for sharing clinical data. IP rights and making industry friendly structures that allow research and opening up data were also mentioned; a novel approach to allow modelling data without sharing it from specific engines/devices was given as an example of this. The general lack of published data in a relatively open field was also talked about, and solving this problem alone (e.g. only 5-10% of data was currently published for EPSRC research) would be a huge achievement in itself (even without thinking about access to data from industrial collaborations).

On a positive and conclusory note, panelists were asked to comment on how advancement would happen due to IoT and Open Data. Answers ranged from not needing to ask permission to use data, the step change in how we will live, to the fact that funders are supportive and the increase in computational skills. The most powerful and thought provoking statement was that the most innovation will happen by changes in our thinking:

thinking about what we want and having the ideas and imagination to drive towards these goals.

The video of the discussion panel is available on the [Institute's YouTube channel](#).

Sustainable Software Practice

The panel members were Daniel S. Katz (National Center for Supercomputing Applications), Jonah Duckles (Software Carpentry Foundation), Clemence Tanzi (qLegal), Neil Chue Hong (Software Sustainability Institute), Melody Sandells (CORES Science & Engineering), Mike Croucher (University of Sheffield) and the panel chair was Institute Deputy Director, Simon Hettrick.

This discussion panel focused largely on training and understanding what researchers do. The panel spoke about the need to sit with researchers and the danger of offering them inadequate training. There is a need to increase the number of people with the necessary skills and abilities but also to focus on the researcher's concerns, their research question, not just technical geekery, by having topic rich conversations with the problem holders.

Culture was also highlighted with an interesting analogy to the Open Source Software Community, where community recognition was made possible by producing good code. In the academic community, that same recognition doesn't exist, which makes the need for software citation even more important, and therefore it is key for the academic/research community to look at other successful ways of giving software recognition.

It is necessary to not only train researchers in software competencies but also train them in software sustainability practices such as being able to successfully win funds to help support software development as part of their research.

Culture is seen as very important: if the leaders in an organisation don't understand the negative impact of non-reproducible research, then how can they support the drive to make research better, so training and education are needed at all levels. In order to drive culture change, there needs to be a move towards what software sustainability can bring to research, rather than just being a niche and geeky subject, and think about how we as the research software community can make ourselves more accessible to those we are seeking to help.

There is a need to bring together early career researchers and University Presidents so they can understand each other's needs and goals. The type of culture change is already underway (e.g. [Imagining Tomorrow's University](#)) and could well be the pattern of engagement required across Institutions.

Throughout the discussion, there was a general awareness that culture is changing but that it is probably another ten years before you can just hand someone a Git link and know what to do with it implicitly.

Opportunities and skill sets in the academic sector are not standing still. There seems to be more choice now and need for different skill sets even if the reward structures are not yet in place. For example, post doctoral staff face so many choices, many ways to contribute and still have a career in academia (e.g. the [RSE](#) path) than taking the traditional PhD to Lecturer route. There was also a statement that upskilling research administrative staff in techniques such as text analysis and better data skills would improve their ability to support research. As well as the productivity argument for better skills the economic argument can be very persuasive also, especially to senior management in academic organisations. For example, a 10% efficiency due to better skills can represent £1M worth of saving for a £10M investment. By surfacing these economic arguments to more senior managers the skills argument can get buy-in from some of the key decision makers rather than being grass roots level only.

Additionally, this discussion panel also proposed that there should be a case made for increasing base-level skills; i.e., low-cost training according to researchers' needs. The suggested training includes version control (e.g., [Git](#)), testing, having a license, automated build, using systems such as [Sphinx](#) to document as you go, think about coding standards—i.e., taking inspiration from community standards such as [PEP 8](#). As well as techniques, the panel agreed that a change is needed in people's productivity by making easier user interfaces. An example is Docker, which is in some way an easier interface to operating system Kernels. Backward compatibility is also important: how to maintain old tools and code. An example of this raised was Mathematica 5 vs Mathematica 10. There is only a ten-year difference between product versions but the new version won't run code from the old version. This type of scenario makes researchers wary of using new software & technology. The sensitivities and effort around re-work and bringing this old things up to date when pushing for modern tool and technology usage needs to be kept in mind and somehow alleviated or mitigated as we push for better sustainable software practices.

A closing remark and possible way forward is to develop [communities of practice](#), to encourage publishing data and software papers and to bring more sustainable software practices to domains and across functions from within.

Collaborative Ideas

The [collaborative ideas session](#) at CW17 brought together research software engineers and people who work in similar domains. They had one hour to identify a problem they faced in their work or domains that could use better software and then outline a proposed solution, something they could make progress on in the 24 hours of the Hack Day. There are a strong networking and social aspects to the Collaborative Ideas sessions: they are as much about coming up with a Hack Day idea as getting to know and working with people from different Institutions, focus and at career stages.

The ideas generated were broadly in line with the themes of the workshop: IoT, Open Data and the mandatory Software Sustainability theme at all of the Collaborations Workshops. You can browse the [list of collaborative ideas](#) that were submitted. After the collaborative ideas session, the ideas are printed, and attendees get to vote on their preferred ideas. The

top voted ideas at this year's CW17 were [One-Click Best Practice](#) and [Visualisation of Conflict Migration](#). Each member of the team won a prize (Amazon vouchers). Many of the ideas were pitched as Hack Day ideas (about 16 pitches) so read on to see how the Hack Day unfolded. Interestingly, both winners formed strong Hack Day teams.

CW17 close (but it's not over!)

CW17 came to a close at 5pm on Tuesday 28th March. This was the main part of the workshop, with nearly 80 delegates that consisted of the keynotes, lightning talks, tours, mini-workshops, collaborative ideas sessions and speed blogging sessions, prizes and lots of networking. 60 people stayed for the Hack-Day evening session and 50 attended all the Hack Day.

CW17 Hack Day (HD)

The CW17 HD started off on the evening of 28th March with an introduction to how things are run and an excellent talk by the Institute's RSG lead, Steve Crouch, on technical choices ([and how to also have fun!](#)). The introduction was interrupted by the mandatory arrival of a mountain of pizza and drinks to fuel everyone up for the gruelling day ahead.

Once the technical choices talk was complete, 16 ideas in total were pitched, though not all of them from the collaborative ideas sessions. The pitches are a way to sell the idea to the audience to let them know what they can work on and which team they want to be part of. There was much horse trading and by the morning of the Hack Day we had six confirmed teams.

The [HD judges](#) did a sterling job. Each team was visited in the morning and the afternoon to see how they were progressing and especially to assess them on how well they were working together. Olivier Philippe from the Institute's Policy team put together a more advanced linear model based normalisation method—part of our drive to ensure fair scoring of entries and across judges.

One of the wonderful aspects of the HD is that people have a chance to try something new, learn something new, practise collaborative work, and get something tangible done in a short space of time often within a new environment and language. As they have often worked effectively with a new set of people there is a strong possibility of future collaborations.

After nearly a day of hacking and working together, each team had five minutes to explain how they [met the judging criteria](#) and show the features and functionality of their new baby. Was the entry novel? Was it potentially impactful? Were best practice in infrastructure used? Was the demo and presentation informative? Was their transparency in what had been done and what was the future potential? These were what the judges were now looking for.

It was very difficult to judge the entries. Judges were choosing among excellent entries, and all teams put in some masterful efforts. Ultimately, only two teams could be selected, and the winners were the [Munroe Meter for jargon scoring](#)—each team member won an Amazon

Echo, which plays nicely with the [IFTTT](#) service and thus the first prize was in line with the IoT theme of the workshop. Runner-ups were [One Click Best Practice](#), and each team member won a Raspberry Pi 3 kit with a 36 sensor pack (some people said in the feedback that the 2nd prize was more desirable than the first!). It's interesting to note that both of these were productivity enhancing tools: [One-Click](#) takes the burden off setting up your development/project environment, and [Munroe Meter](#) helps to check the text in papers, proposals, etc., to make sure they are easier to understand. Take a look at [all the Hack Day entries](#).

Thank you and acknowledgements

Many people come together to offer advice, resource and help running the workshop in addition to the Institute staff. Without them (and the rest of the CW delegates), the Collaboration Workshops would not be able to take place.

We extend our thanks to everyone who contributed to making CW17 a very successful event:

- [Our Sponsors](#)
- Our attendees
- The [MEETinLEEDS](#) team and the building staff at [LUBS](#)
- [Our Steering committee](#)
- [Our Organising committee](#), [Events team](#) and [staff](#)
- [Our Funders](#)

